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**Synergistic Applications of Virtual, Augmented, and Mixed Reality
Technologies with Psychedelic-Assisted Psychotherapy**

By: Alexandra M Plesner
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This thesis laid the foundation for ongoing research into integration, regenerative design, ritual frameworks, and creative problem-solving at the intersection of psychedelics and design. It also informs a series of speculative design projects and tools.

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Abstract

Psychedelic drugs have lately made waves in mainstream media, popularised as The Psychedelic Renaissance. Modern clinical research on psychedelics demonstrates promising results for treating various clinical conditions when psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy is delivered to appropriately screened participants and in controlled settings. Findings showed that due to psychedelics' characteristic of being non-specific amplifiers, individual and contextual factors (i.e., set and setting) shape the psychedelic experience and ultimately determine therapeutic outcomes. This emphasises the need to investigate and learn from ancient traditions, nature, and new technologies to optimise set and setting. Psychedelic drugs and technologies, such as virtual, augmented and mixed reality, have traits of altering common consciousness and evoking awe.

In this review, a structured search through databases was performed, investigating the role of context, psychedelics, and virtual, augmented and mixed reality technologies—and their functional relationship. The aim was to outline the current state of research, derive and describe a structured associated potential psychotherapeutic intervention. Findings suggest a potential synergistic application in clinical and recreational settings, which might result in better physical and psychological outcomes, due to but not limited to managing consistency in environmental settings, a highly bespoke experience, allowing for a feeling of ownership, better long-term economic viability, and perhaps achieving significant effect with lower doses of a given psychedelic compound.

Keywords: Psychedelics • Hallucinogen • Entheogen • Mystical experience • Setting • Virtual Reality • Augmented Reality • Mixed Reality • Context • Environment

Introduction

New technological advances in highly immersive virtual, augmented and mixed reality is in synergy with a vital renaissance in psychedelic research (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Witt, 2018). A resurrection of research and development of psychedelic compounds since the U.S. Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) classified psychedelics as Schedule I substances under the Controlled Substances Act (Pugh et al., 2020).

Psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy

Classic psychedelics such as psilocybin, lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), ketamine, N-dimethyltryptamine (DMT), and 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) have a long history of research (Carhart-Harris & Goodwin, 2017). Human history with psychedelics

is historical, with the consumption of mind-altering plants even being attributed to the enhancement of human cognition across evolution (Winkelman, 2021).

Research revealed positive and enduring results of psychedelics for the treatment of depression (Carhart-Harris et al., 2021), post-traumatic stress disorder (Mithoefer et al., 2019), Alzheimer's Disease and dementia (Vann Jones & O'Kelly, 2020), addictions (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018), social anxiety (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018), eating disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and neurorehabilitation and cognitive enhancement (Rastelli et al., 2022).

These compounds increase cellular and molecular neuroplasticity (Barrett et al., 2020; Cavarra et al., 2022; de Vos et al., 2021). The increase in neuroplasticity is thought to be the reason for increased environmental and information sensitivity and suggestibility (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019; Carhart-Harris et al., 2018) even a month after a single high dosage (Barrett et al., 2020). Psychedelics are also known to be non-specific amplifiers (Grof, 2019), meaning they amplify whatever feelings and sensations may arise during a psychedelic experience. Part of their impact has been attributed to the so-called mystical experience and its significance in inducing sustained positive changes (Griffiths et al., 2006; de Vos et al., 2021; Winkelman, 2021).

Any therapy's impact and quality depend on two key factors: set (the participant's mindset) and setting (the environment). Subsequently, the state of sensitivity and fragility induced by psychedelics suggests that those key factors are even more vital and must be considered for psychedelic-assisted therapy (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Pollan, 2018).

In summary, these features and the quality of integration of the psychedelic experiences are thought to determine the therapeutic outcomes.

Carhart-Harris et al. propose that in this plastic state the brain becomes acutely sensitive to both internal and external influences, in other words the set and setting respectively. Cortical plasticity thus provides the physiological link between psychedelics and the importance of context. (Simmons, 2022, para. 9)

Psychotherapy augmented through virtual and mixed reality

Virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality are immersive computer-mediated and interactive experiences in which the user perceives and interacts with a simulated environment via a human-computer interface (Georgiev et al., 2021). Virtual reality immerses the user in a fully virtual world. Augmented reality overlays virtual elements in the real-world environment. Mixed reality, also called hybrid reality, overlays elements and blends virtual and augmented reality by anchoring virtual elements to the real world (Bharadwaj, 2017).

The user still sees the natural world as it is but simultaneously experiences a digital layer with interactive elements through hardware such as augmented reality glasses or a mobile device like the iPhone.

Virtual reality and mixed reality have demonstrated promising and enduring results in the treatment of anxiety and stress-related disorders (Boeldt et al., 2019; Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021), schizophrenia (Bisso et al., 2020), addictive disorders (Segawa et al., 2020), phobia (De Witte et al., 2020), eating disorders (Riva et al., 2021), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), pain management, neurorehabilitation and cognitive enhancement (Georgiev et al., 2021).

Therapeutic applications of non-ordinary states similar to those induced with psychedelics are also known to be evoked through sensory stimulation (Bartossek et al., 2021). Beyond the augmented reality filter that gained popularity through social media networks, virtual reality and mixed reality are used to alter the sensory experience of users, including evoking particular mental states and emotional responses, for example, the sense of awe (Stepanova et al., 2019; Stepanova et al., 2019).

The capacity of virtual reality to affect neuroplasticity (Georgiev et al., 2021), inducing both short and long-term changes in the brain (Cheung et al., 2014), shows therapeutic potential for applications similar to or in synergy with psychedelic compounds (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

Additionally, virtual reality stimulates visually altered perception experiences like psychedelics (Bisso et al., 2020; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Rastelli et al., 2022). Although less common than virtual reality, mixed reality shows its potential by allowing the preservation of the natural physical environment whilst offering additional virtual stimuli, allowing the patient to interact with their actual physical environment, the therapist and virtual objects (De Witte et al., 2020).

Because immersive realities are a narrative medium, they hold the potential to redesign the story of past experiences and induce a sense of ownership and playfulness to redesign individual life events into an integrated process of personal development, also for healthy individuals (Georgiev et al., 2021; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Sekula et al., 2022). Despite the topic's relevance in general and applied psychology, studies have yet to be published testing a combined therapy approach.

Problem statement

Relevant problems of psychedelic-assisted therapy are (a) a lack of congruence; (b) limitations and impact of set and setting; (c) the extensive integration phase starting as early

as the comedown phase; and (d) the problem of patients to recall insights directly after the dosing session (Janikian, 2021).

The psychedelic journey is usually divided into three phases preparation, dosing, and integration (Garcia-Romeu et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2008). In clinical models, we see predominantly internally designed experiences where the patient puts on blindfolds during the dosing session, is encouraged to surrender to the experience, often lying down in a room and is instructed not to interact with the surroundings (Koslowski et al., 2021). Contrary to the classic clinical setting, externally oriented experiences are often found in retreat models and recreational use, which aligns with some indigenous traditions that encourage not to go inwards but rather to engage with nature or keep the focus on something like an altar (Janikian, 2021).

Primarily due to logistical and financial limitations, the clinical setting is bound to a therapy room which leads to the segmentation into distinct, separate treatment phases as mentioned above (preparation, dosing, and integration), which not only disrupts a fluid psychedelic journey but more so contributes to a lack of consistency between sessions (Griffiths et al., 2016; Sekula et al., 2022). Furthermore, individual trials, preparation and integration may be based at different locations (Sekula et al., 2022), involve different or a change of therapists (Fuentes et al., 2020), and the use of various aids, specifically music (Kaelen et al., 2018), extend the discontinuity further.

Clinical settings can also cause anxieties or phobias, such as iatrophobia – the fear of doctors, medical care, or the medical care system. This potentially negatively impacts the patient's mindset, psychedelic experience, and treatment outcome and affects the relationships with healthcare professionals (Hollander & Greene, 2019).

Psychedelic experiences are profound, and integration work is vital to therapeutic success. The long-lasting increased neuroplasticity and in addition to that, increased sensitivity (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019; Carhart-Harris et al., 2017; Carhart-Harris et al., 2018) are challenging for the integration phase, not only for the current clinical model but also for retreat models and recreational use.

In contrast to clinical settings, a nature-based setting ensures a relaxed, primaeval, connected, and multi-sensory experience through the entire psychedelic trip, ideally extending into comedown and further integration (Sekula et al., 2022; Winkelman, 2021). Notably, a setting in nature has its own challenge, like potential changes in weather, distance to clinical equipment and other disturbances (Gandy et al., 2020).

Both clinical and natural settings have pros and cons. The potential synergistic effects between psychedelic administration and nature contact for improving mental health are verifiable.

Relevance of the topic in general

There is growing commercial, medical and personal interest in psychedelics and virtual reality for therapy. The use of hallucinogens has increased since 2020, and "in 2021, 8% of young adults reported past-year hallucinogen use, representing an all-time high since the category was first surveyed in 1988" by comparison, "in 2011, only 3% reported use", only MDMA showed "statistically significant decreases within one year as well as the past five years – from 5% in both 2016 and 2020 to 3% in 2021" (National Institutes of Health, 2022, para. 7).

Dr Carhart-Harris confirms, "We've actually seen, looking at some recent data, that use of psychedelics over the last 10 years has increased exponentially" (O'Hare, 2021, para. 13). Additionally, the demand for virtual and mixed reality is high, with sales of virtual reality goggles rising 350% during the lockdown (Eccles, 2021). A commercial interest is currently predominantly sitting in entertainment, but investors and companies are turning their attention to those technologies to enhance the impact and accessibility of healthcare treatments. Virtual and mixed reality are hoped to reduce resource issues for psychedelic-assisted therapies, thereby also lowering treatment costs (Psychedelic-assisted Therapy Enhanced Through VR Technology, 2021).

Virtual reality-assisted and psychedelic-assisted therapies offer numerous benefits, both for the clinician and the patient, such as availability, individualisation, not being physically addicting, free from side effects compared to traditional medication, long-lasting and controllable (Gómez-Busto & Ortiz, 2020).

Indeed, the world's first clinical trial of virtual reality modulate psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy on recruited patients, a joint collaboration between the Australian biotech and psychedelic startup Enosis Therapeutics, Swinburne University and the Psychedelic Society of Belgium, was conducted and completed in the Netherlands in 2022 and the promising results are due to be published (Enosis Therapeutics, 2022).

Relevance of the topic within applied psychology

A disruption of the therapeutic process and lack of congruence throughout treatment could result in psychological side effects such as paranoia and trauma and diminish the positive outcomes over time (Johnstad, 2021; Sekula et al., 2022). Considering how much

the environment impacts each phase of the treatment, and therefore not only the therapeutic session but also the outcome (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018), it seems imperative to put extra attention to the environmental setting and consistency of the entire process (Sekula et al., 2022).

Virtual and mixed reality has the potential to solve the practical problems of congruence, consistency, accessibility, efficacy, resources, individualisation, location, set/setting and overall management of psychedelic-assisted therapy (Aday et al., 2020; Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Gandy et al., 2020; Kettner et al., 2019; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Payne et al., 2021; Sekula et al., 2022; Winkelman, 2021).

Moroz and Carhart-Harris (2018) write that although in its infancy, a dual approach might increase the efficacy of each paradigm of psychedelic therapy due to synergistic coupling and the ability to tailor bespoke therapies for particular individuals and groups.

The ability of psychedelics to increase presence and the ability of virtual reality to provide controlled sensory stimuli creates a potential for powerful bespoke treatment solutions. The individual interventions not only complement each other but offer synergistic interactions whereby each increases the efficacy of the other. (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018, p. 2).

Such increases in effectiveness could lead to better accessibility of psychedelic-assisted therapy to patients, a potential decrease of the dose of a given psychedelic compound with continued effectiveness (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018), optimisation and tailoring of the environment and therapeutic setting (Aday et al., 2020; Sekula et al., 2022). Accessibility and economic viability are a key factor for making psychedelic-assisted therapy available in future, given that the World Health Organisation (2021) estimates "approximately 280 million people in the world" to have depression (para. 1); this equals 3.8% of the entire population.

Objective

This written work aims to (a) give an overview of the current research; (b) provide an overview of central theories and empirical findings; (c) suggest possible applications for virtual and mixed reality for psychedelic-assisted therapy; and (d) change the narrative positively around these compounds, while emphasising the proven importance of context (set and setting) for risk and harm reduction and augmentation of their healing benefits.

Here, unique features of digital technologies such as virtual reality or mixed reality and their functional relationship with psychedelics are investigated, followed by a theoretical exploration of the synergetic application for therapy, which might result in better physical and

psychological outcomes, due but not limited to managing consistency in environmental settings.

Theoretical background

Material and methods

A literature review was conducted using the databases: PubMed, Nature, Frontiers, ResearchGate, SagePub, National Library of Medicine, and SpringerLink, searching for "psychedelic AND assisted AND psychotherapy," "psilocybin AND assisted AND psychotherapy," "psychedelic AND enhanced AND psychotherapy," "psychedelics AND virtual reality," "psychedelics AND mixed reality," "virtual reality AND therapy," "psychedelics AND setting AND virtual reality," and "psychedelics AND nature"; as well as the input of various combinations of the following keywords: "psychedelic", "virtual reality", "augmented reality", "mixed reality", "context", and "setting". Some other studies were obtained through screening references from relevant articles.

Only studies and articles written in English, published in 2018 and after that, using a psychedelic or empathogen substance (i.e., LSD, psilocybin, MDMA, ayahuasca, ketamine, DMT, 5-MeO-DMT, mescaline), using virtual, mixed or altered reality, or a combination of psychedelics and virtual reality, or had a focus on 'setting' were included.

Many institutions driving the new wave of psychedelic and virtual and mixed reality research are large pharmaceutical and commercial companies. This research and the general hype around these topics could bias the results.

Results

Over 61.500 articles and studies resulted from the search. After screening titles and abstracts according to the above-mentioned criteria, approximately 180 were retained after the full-text screening, and some were added after an iterative reference list search. The most relevant findings (year, sample, method, measurement, focus, results) of 20 studies and articles are summarised in the theoretical background and highlighted:

- the characteristics of classic psychedelics;
- virtual and mixed reality for therapy;
- the potential combined application of virtual and mixed reality for psychedelic-assisted therapy.

The current state of research – central theories

Here, the current state of research is categorised into (a) psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy; (b) virtual, mixed, and augmented reality-assisted psychotherapy; (c) nature and therapeutic settings; and (d) potential synergetic application.

Psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy

The therapeutic outcome of therapy is fundamentally reliant on context (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). The individual set and contextual setting factors play an essential role in some of the observed clinical gains with psychedelics-assisted psychotherapy (Cavarra et al., 2022; Pollan, 2018).

Firstly, classic psychedelics increase neuroplasticity (Cavarra et al., 2022; Stoliker et al., 2022; de Vos et al., 2021) along with environmental sensitivity, increased vulnerability and suggestibility (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Cavarra et al., 2022) both during the dosing session itself and in the following days (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). Therefore it is reasoned that a disregard for context could render a psychedelic experience ineffective and potentially harmful (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). Given that the acute effect of a substance usually lasts several hours (Koslowski et al., 2021), setting for psychedelic-assisted therapy is imperative.

Secondly, the significant changes in functional connections across the brain are not a temporary phenomenon during the dosing session but are continuously altered from baseline one week up to one month or longer post-psychedelic dosing, for example, with the psychedelic compound psilocybin (Barrett et al., 2020).

Additionally, the importance of therapeutic alliance is established in mental healthcare, and research agrees that it is even more salient in the fertile state of an individual during and after a long-lasting psychedelic experience (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Cavarra et al., 2022).

To explain the effects of psychedelic therapy on the brain through an overarching theoretical model, Carhart-Harris and Friston (2019) formulated the relaxed beliefs under psychedelics (REBUS) and the anarchic brain describing that psychedelics liberate bottom-up information flow, relaxing precision from rational-logical thinking to associative-instinctual thinking (Carhart-Harris et al., 2014; Cavarra et al., 2022; Koslowski et al., 2021). This theory proposes that "psychedelic therapy can be helpful for such a broad range of disorders precisely because psychedelics work pharmacologically (5-HT_{2A}augmented reality agonism) and neurophysiologically (increased excitability of deep-layer pyramidal neurons)" (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019, p. 334), relaxing said

precision, leading to profound destabilisation of beliefs, which in turn renders a high sensitivity to context (Koslowski et al., 2021).

Davis et al. (2020) elaborate that psychological theories, such as psychological flexibility, emerge from Contextual Behavioral Science (CBS) concepts, and relational frame theory may be fit to address the phenomenological and awe experience of psychedelics that are typical in psychedelic-assisted therapy. The destabilisation of assumptions (Koslowski et al., 2021) at higher levels of information processing is precisely where psychedelics can augment psychotherapy, challenging and changing dysfunctional belief structures (Cavarra et al., 2022; Koslowski et al., 2021) through continuous effective integration post the dosing session (Koslowski et al., 2021; Stoliker et al., 2022).

The central argument, which all studies agree on and no conflicting theory has been found, is that context makes or breaks the therapeutic efficacy of psychedelic-augmented psychotherapy.

Virtual, mixed, and augmented reality-assisted psychotherapy

Generally, the researched papers differentiate primarily between a fully immersive virtual reality, and reality-enhancing augmented and mixed reality.

Mixed reality shows several advantages compared to the more commonly researched virtual reality (Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021). A fully immersive virtual reality experience means a person enters an entirely virtual world through special hardware such as a head-mounted display. The ultimate goal is to eliminate sensory input from the real world as much as possible to support sustaining the illusion that the virtual world is the actual reality (Georgiev et al., 2021). In turn, augmented and mixed reality are hybrids in which real and virtual elements overlay and allow the user to interact with the real and virtual worlds simultaneously.

The research agrees, similar to psychedelic-assisted therapy, with the importance of context, meaning the intentions of the user as well as the design of the setting (Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021; Stepanova et al., 2019), since virtual reality triggers neuroplasticity and neurogenesis, similar to psychedelics (Georgiev et al., 2021; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

Seabrook et al. (2020) mention Kaplan's Attention Restoration Theory, a useful framework for understanding how altered realities may foster present-moment awareness. Computer-generated or augmented realities allow access to immense amounts of computer-stored data and variables to simulate and enhance any imaginable environment (Georgiev et al., 2021).

Environments that are restorative according to the Attention Restoration Theory, a) provide the individual with a pause from the everyday environment, b) have attention anchors that maintain engagement, c) contain elements and features that enable to hold said attention with small effort, and d) support a personal mission (Seabrook et al., 2020). All these elements are part of the virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality experience, supporting mindfulness practice and therapeutic efficiency (Georgiev et al., 2021; Riches et al., 2021; Seabrook et al., 2020).

Rastelli et al. (2022) measured the cognitive flexibility of 52 participants through behavioural tasks after exposure to virtual reality panoramic videos and their hallucinatory-like counterparts generated by the DeepDream algorithm, initially derived from a Google project to develop intelligent image recognition software (Bulkeley, 2015). Results suggested that simulated altered perceptual phenomenology enhances cognitive flexibility comparable to psychedelics (Rastelli et al., 2022).

Virtual environments allow for a feeling of awe and not only simulate and augment the physical environment with natural beauty (Georgiev et al., 2021), suggesting emotional rehabilitation (Seabrook et al., 2020) but also allow for tailoring to the individual need and precise control over setting and stimuli (Ma et al., 2021; Stepanova et al., 2019).

Experiences shape how an individual perceives their life story forms social and behavioural patterns and manages memory. Immersion in virtual reality creates opportunities to reshape an individual's narrative of past experiences, perceptions of the self, and the world due to its narrative abilities (Georgiev et al., 2021; Gómez-Busto & Ortiz, 2020).

Georgiev et al. (2021) emphasise that virtual reality technologies are enjoyable and engaging, offer a safe and controlled environment, are ideally suited to aid self-improvement, and have furthermore shown promise for better functional outcomes, including the recovery of the damaged neural tissue in rehabilitation processes.

The body model theory of the somatosensory cortex (Brecht, 2017; Georgiev et al., 2021) explains that the parietal lobe, actively involved in virtual reality experiences, contains (a) the primary somatosensory cortex, which includes somatic sensations and the feeling of embodiment; (b) the angular gyrus, which includes memory and imagination; and (c) the precuneus, which includes visuospatial imagery, first-person perspective, presence or experiencing agency.

Lastly, virtual and mixed realities give the user a sense of ownership (Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021; Seabrook et al., 2020; Sekula et al., 2022; Stepanova et al., 2019).

Nature and the therapeutic setting

In contrast to clinical models for therapeutic psychedelic administration, which are mainly internally designed experiences within a built environment (Koslowski et al., 2021), nature-based settings promise to have psychologically soothing effects and potentially enhance nature-relatedness (Frecka et al., 2022; Gandy et al., 2020; Kettner et al., 2019). Gandy et al. (2020) write that the healing effects of nature might be maximised through a complementary therapeutic psychedelic administration.

In alignment with the aforementioned Attention Restoration Theory, Stepanova et al. (2019) compared their virtual experience to the effect of walking in a park, describing that when aiming to achieve great results with virtual reality therapy, it is important for the patient to feel safe at the starting point of the experience for them to be open and without resistance (Stepanova et al., 2019). The results of a psychedelic experience depend on the individuals' openness to the experience and the feeling of safety from the onset until the comedown phase (Cavarra et al., 2022; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

Nature-based settings can have a calming effect on the individual in all stages of the therapeutic process (Frecka et al., 2022; Gandy et al., 2020). Both nature exposure and therapeutic psychedelic administration have been closely tied with effects such as decreased rumination, enhanced connectedness, mindfulness, state of awe, and other processes linked to mental health improvement (Gandy et al., 2020). Ulrich's Stress Reduction Theory (SRT) explains that the presence of natural elements creates positive emotional and physiological reactions (Jiang et al., 2020), eases our state of alertness and reduces mental fatigue (Gandy et al., 2020).

Natural settings and rituals are essential characteristics of shamanic healing, and the adoption of these frameworks is to be beneficial for psychedelic-assisted therapy. Winkelman (2021) further extends that "idiosyncratic personality dynamics, mood and expectations" (p. 1) influence the psychedelic experience and therapeutic outcome as much as the social environment and cultural beliefs of a person.

The speed of movement versus the complexity of design elements is essential for virtual reality experiences, as justified by Jiang et al. (2020) who looked at the impacts of landscape greenness and complexity on humans' mental status in the context of speed of movement.

Potential synergetic application

Both virtual reality and psychedelics have demonstrated promising results in the treatment of anxiety, depression, eating disorders cognitive functioning (Boeldt et al., 2019;

Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021), Riva et al., 2021; Georgiev et al., 2021; Carhart-Harris et al., 2021; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Rastelli et al., 2022).

An increase in neuroplasticity and neurogenesis has been proven in both virtual reality and psychedelic treatments (Barrett et al., 2020; Cavarra et al., 2022; Georgiev et al., 2021; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; de Vos et al., 2021).

The need to create a supportive set and setting is widely accepted to be a key factor for a positive therapeutic outcome among psychedelic and virtual reality-assisted therapy researchers. As mentioned previously, the research found that virtual reality can provide a pleasant, easy, and safe setting, potentially improving some treatments, such as psychedelic-assisted therapy (Aday et al., 2020).

Moroz and Carhart-Harris (2018) theorise that virtual reality and psychedelics complement each other and potentially increase the efficacy of the other. The authors write about the openness to absorbing and self-altering experiences. They argue that treatments involving virtual reality and psychedelics can take patients even further, resulting in greater susceptibility and great treatment success.

Virtual reality can simulate the visual phenomenology of a psychedelic trip (Aday et al., 2020), which suggests it be a potential tool to prepare participants for their psychedelic therapy session, helping them to transition from a normal state of consciousness to an altered state of consciousness. Aday et al. (2020) further write that virtual reality could optimise and tailor the therapeutic setting during the transition from the normal state of consciousness to an altered state, the comedown phase, integration sessions and even during the trip. Indeed the Australian startup Enosis Therapeutics is testing a “Rescue virtual reality” protocol, which potentially pulls patients transiently out of the experience when it becomes too overwhelming or harmful (Enosis Therapeutics, 2022).

A recent meta-analysis showed that a wide range of virtual reality interventions, in particular when using nature-based audio-visual stimuli, reliably facilitate a state of relaxation (Riches et al., 2021), highlighting virtual reality's potential for use in conjunction with psychedelic therapy, which can be viewed as challenging by some patients. Sekula et al. (2022) suggest that a reliable virtual reality setting may mitigate the adverse psychological states, mobilising the effects of each phase of the psychedelic experience.

According to the emotional processing theory, fear is a cognitive structure and a learned program to protect oneself from further danger and pain (Gómez-Busto & Ortiz, 2020). Generally, both the use of virtual reality (as a narrative medium) and psychedelics (as a gateway opener) show promising results for patients to overcome past programming and

take agency of their life story (Georgiev et al., 2021; Gómez-Busto & Ortiz, 2020; Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Sekula et al., 2022).

Moreover, Rastelli et al. (2020) mention that similar brain patterns can be observed between psychedelic drugs and artificially-induced altered perceptual phenomenology, with increased entropic brain dynamics and global functional connectivity.

"Rather than deciding which novel intervention holds the greatest potential for treatment, we advance a theory that, in many cases, an optimum solution necessarily incorporates both techniques" (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018, p. 1).

The current state of research – empirical findings

The studies and articles reviewed found benefits and limitations of psychedelics and looked at the importance of setting for both virtual reality and psychedelics augmented therapy (Aday et al., 2020; Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Frecska et al., 2022; Gandy et al., 2020; Koslowski et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021; Sekula et al., 2022).

Context

Psychedelic experiences are never alike, and it is a journey. Koslowski et al. (2021) emphasise that the experience has several stages and the longevity of such stages. A peak experience can improve psychological well-being for up to two weeks and more following the psychedelic administration. Challenging experiences predict a deflation of any positive effect or effectively can worsen the situation for a patient over time (Barrett et al., 2020; Koslowski et al., 2021).

Recent hypotheses and findings suggest that the increased neuroplasticity (effects of serotonin and serotonin 2A receptor agonism) increases the sensitivity to context in psychedelic experience extraordinarily (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). As mentioned before, these findings make the context (i.e., set and setting) a key component in shaping the psychedelic experience and determining the therapeutic outcome over time (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Davis et al., 2020; Koslowski et al., 2021).

However, few controlled studies investigated the direct relationship between psychedelics and context (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018), for example, the music playlists' impact.

A decreased top-down effective connectivity from the resting state networks associated with the ingestion of psychedelics (Stoliker et al., 2022) and its effect on the amygdala partially remains for up to one month post-psilocybin intake (Barrett et al., 2020). Consequently, the long-lasting effect of psychedelics emphasises enduring vulnerability to

set and setting and draws attention to the importance of integration, the phase post-psychedelic intake, where insights gained during the experience are addressed, and those learnings are integrated into daily life (Barrett et al., 2020; Cavarra et al., 2022; Stoliker et al., 2022).

Trials have paid particular attention to context and the design of the clinical setting, from thoughtfully selected music playlists to lighting and decoration of the room with natural elements (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). However, factoring in context comes with challenges since it incorporates practical and financial burdens.

Attention and positive expectations also bias the outcome of such clinical trials. Patients have very carefully prepared settings and at least two very attentive mental health professionals who support them throughout the entire experience (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018). The set-up of a psychedelic experience is very unusual in scale and effort compared to classic mental healthcare services. The patients will likely receive more attention in those trials than they did in the years leading up to it by standard health care.

Other limitations are small sample sizes, difficulties in successfully blinding (Koslowski et al., 2021), "the potential for hype" (Davis et al., 2020, p. 6), and the highly suggestible state of the patient post-session (Cavarra et al., 2022) to bias study outcomes of psychedelics. Stoliker et al. (2022) add that some participants of clinical trials have been given the psychedelic compound in an MRI scan rather than a soothing natural or at least optimised clinical environment, which would have influenced the subjective and objective outcome and added anxiety.

In their article, Carhart-Harris et al. (2018) draw attention to the fact that—very much in contradiction to the critical role context plays in psychedelic administration—in the earliest known use of LSD, set and setting have been mainly uncontrolled and positive psychological effects were reported despite of it. However, the authors further mention that the outcomes were significantly less favourable when 'set' and 'setting' were deliberately neglected or manipulated negatively.

16 Virtual and augmented worlds

Georgiev et al. (2021) explain that artificially-induced altered perceptual phenomenology can draw from an infinite digital information source and generate specific virtual environments that can be significantly individualised for patients' needs at any time. Virtual reality offers immersion and improves cognitive functions through its neurobiological effects on neuronal plasticity (Georgiev et al., 2021).

This immersive and narrative nature of virtual reality, mixed reality and augmented reality technologies induce a sense of ownership, control and presence (Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021). Positive aspects of this kind of technology-assisted psychotherapy seem to be associated with the high adaptability and controllability of virtual environments (Ma et al., 2021). Investigations suggest that well-designed virtual reality can have a relaxing and soothing effect on the patient (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Seabrook et al., 2022; Stepanova et al., 2019).

Seabrook et al. (2022) found that as the virtual environment allowed the participants to explore their surroundings and allowed them to select anchor points, they felt a sense of presence and safety. The anchoring is a key element that equips the user against potential discomfort and helps orient oneself in a non-familiar environment (Stepanova et al., 2019).

Overall, virtual experiences have potential short and long-term positive outcomes such as pro-social behaviour, pro-environmental attitudes, mental and physical health improvements (Stepanova et al., 2019). While virtual reality has the user plunge into an entirely virtual environment, Ma et al. (2021) suggest that augmented reality can be of even greater efficiency since the user remains in the real world while simultaneously interacting with virtual elements. When for example, walking through the virtual world (without being an avatar), patients reported feeling disconnected from their bodies (Stepanova et al., 2019). Mixed and augmented reality technology allows the user to experience an augmentation of everyday reality, but further research is needed to understand details.

Above all, virtual reality augmented reality, and mixed reality technologies can solve the problem of congruity of therapy. Since it is portable, personalisable and controllable, it can offer a consistent therapeutic environment from the therapy room to the patient's home (Ma et al., 2021).

Despite those potential benefits, these novel technologies are inaccessible to most. The development of standardised therapy, safety and hygiene protocols is required as well as the building of infrastructure and therapist training, all of which make it very cost-intensive to start with, although potentially economically viable long-term approach (Ma et al., 2021; Stepanova et al., 2019).

There are several limitations in looking at the findings; for example, the studies were conducted within an academic context without standardisation, and the effectiveness is often not backed by empirical evidence (Ma et al., 2021). Also, direct evidence for the underlying changes at the neuron level seems currently out of reach of what is possible in brain imaging (Georgiev et al., 2021). Finally, as Ma et al. (2021) found, the side effects can be motion

sickness and photosensitive seizures. Whereas Stepanova et al. (2019) reported that participants sometimes felt nervous and anxious.

Synergies: psychedelics, virtual reality and nature

Stepanova et al. (2019) further explain that most participants perceived the virtual forest environment as safe and comforting. However, in a few cases, the same forest was considered scary, and users felt anxious and nervous. Such contradictions indicate that experiences are very individual and personal, and so are the reactions to different elements, be they natural or virtual. This has to be factored into the design process of the environment as well as the therapy protocol. Moroz and Carhart-Harris (2018) explain that the slightest changes in light, visuals, or sound profoundly impact patients; emphasising the potential of a bespoke treatment made possible through technology.

Aday et al. (2020) conclude that their findings have proven that psychedelic compounds and virtual reality states can be effective in synergy. Similar brain patterns have been found when looking at psychedelic compounds and artificially-induced altered perceptual phenomenology, with increased neural connectivity and brain entropy (Aday et al., 2020; Rastelli et al., 2022; Sekula et al., 2022).

Both psychedelics and virtual reality evoke awe and have proven their potential in treating phobias, eating disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), addiction, anxiety, depression, schizophrenia, and also physical conditions (Cavarra et al., 2022; Georgiev et al., 2021; Gómez-Busto & Ortiz, 2020; Ma et al., 2021).

Some challenges with full-dose therapeutic psychedelic experiences are:

- the lack of consistency (Sekula et al., 2022);
- the lengthiness of a single dosing session—from up to several hours (adding logistical and financial weight) (Cavarra et al., 2022);
- the unpredictability (no two experiences are alike, and no two patients react alike) (Davis et al., 2020);
- the extended process of integration (Cavarra et al., 2022; Koslowski et al., 2021);
- impaired recollection of insights after the peak (Sekula et al., 2022);
- sterile clinical environments (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018); and
- stress and anxiety before or during dosing (Sekula et al., 2022).

Moroz and Carhart-Harris (2018) believe that by using virtual reality tools for psychedelic-assisted therapy potentially (a) the same therapeutic effects will be achieved with lower dosing; (b) the efficacy of both virtual reality and psychedelic compound is

increased, due to their complementary nature; and (c) the possibility to deliver tailored protocols increases accuracy of dosing and is more time efficient.

A virtual reality modulation of psychedelic-assisted therapy might increase expectations of the efficiency of the therapy (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018). In an interview, Sara Gael, harm reduction officer for MAPS, said that virtual reality potentially could “undermine a patient’s natural ability to interpret the sensations of their trip” (Ruiz, 2022, para. 17) and given the high suggestibility of a person under psychedelics (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018; Davis et al., 2020; Koslowski et al., 2021), virtual reality not only influences the natural journey of a patient but adds potential risks.

A natural environment’s calming and stress-reducing effect (Gandy et al., 2020) can even be achieved within 5–10 minutes spent in a natural setting. Psychedelics foster nature-relatedness (Frecka et al., 2022), and Kettner et al. (2019) found that nature-relatedness remained “elevated 7–12 months post-psilocybin treatment” (p. 12) and in those who completed a two-year follow-up, these changes lasted. The authors recognise the limitations of their study being a small sample size, lack of diversity, lack of control and placebo effect (Kettner et al., 2019).

Studies and articles describe that nature has direct calming benefits, allowing the patient to feel a sense of interconnectedness, but that a natural setting has its own challenges, such as privacy, potential disturbances, weather, and safety (Gandy et al., 2020).

A very pragmatic statement from Gandy et al. (2020) summarises, “some participants may feel more comfortable having these discussions with their therapist in a clinical room, others may feel more comfortable ‘walking and talking’” (p. 9) in a natural environment. Furthermore, this environment might be virtual reality or a clinical setting with augmented reality enhancement.

In conclusion, more research is needed to explore the effectiveness of psychedelics and digitally augmented therapies (or a combination) in various mental and physical disorders, illnesses, and the diversity of cultures and populations.

Intervention-related questions

Two intervention-related research questions for this study are as follows:

1. How can we optimise therapeutic environments and overcome barriers that may obstruct existing psychedelic protocols by leveraging virtual reality’s unique properties?

2. How can we create an experience bridging the virtual and real-world, emerging patience in the healing power of nature settings that speak to human truths, even when external real-world settings are not ideal?

Practical intervention

Mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy – in theory

What would happen if the virtual and real-world boundaries faded? Mixed and augmented reality blend the real with the virtual world, extending the normal world with playful and immersive effects. The technology is already here, with Apple's LiDaugmented reality scanner in most people's pockets via the iPhone (requires iOS 14.0 or later) and Apple's first augmented reality glasses rumoured to launch in 2023 (Bajarin, 2022) – making them more accessible to a broader range of consumers. Mixed and augmented reality have the potential to allow the user to have virtual interactive experiences in their immediate environments, reconnecting people back with their surroundings even when using digital devices.

Minor changes to the surroundings alter the perception of space. For example, when moving into a new home, some objects transform a generic space into something personal, the quintessence of the feeling of home and familiarity. When moving, people tend to take certain elements, potentially with emotional value, with them. As humans, we also like to bring nature into the home through indoor plants and bouquets of flowers.

Being in nature or feeling close to it has proven to positively impact physiological, psychological, and cognitive health (Frecka et al., 2022; Gandy et al., 2020; Winkelman, 2021). A natural setting outdoors with challenges such as changing weather conditions and access to clinical equipment, and the sterile atmosphere of a classic clinical setting could be better. How can a natural setting be brought into a clinical environment? In clinical and therapeutic settings, props are used to soften the space.

The proposal is a novel synergetic therapeutic approach of mixed reality and psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy for a wide range of disorders. For the experience, natural elements can be extended virtually to a physical space, allowing the individual user to create their personal therapeutic surroundings, choosing from visual and audio elements.

In theory, a mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy space meets reality and virtuality halfway. The user might decide to bring the seaside or the woods into the therapy room entirely to their personal liking. This experience might help a patient transition from normal to altered consciousness and then again help the transition from the altered stage back to normal consciousness, having a potentially gentler comedown phase. The

therapist could also wear augmented reality glasses and join the patient's personal landscape.

Integrating some elements of nature into the preparation and integration phases could amplify key therapeutic mechanisms and outcomes (Gandy et al., 2020); when nature is not accessible, mixed reality might offer a solution to bring the idea of nature into an urban space. The patient might feel motivated and encouraged to use his personal mixed reality space as an ongoing resource for mediation and integration therapy post the immediate psychedelic trip.

Other possibilities in function, such as audio journaling, can add to a seamless, engaging and effective therapy session. Technology advances such as responsive AI and biofeedback will continuously improve the treatment experience and outcome and allow for direct and live measuring of the treatment effects (Ma et al., 2021).

Recommend evaluation and effectiveness measures

In order to test the effectiveness of mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy, at first, a functioning prototype based on existing technology using existing hardware ought to be developed including a protocol for psychedelic therapy with mixed reality and the respective software. Testing could be done in collaboration with a clinic and institutions using process evaluation, not only to evaluate the outcomes but also the design and functionality of the intervention.

For one, a quantitative approach with an intervention-specific questionnaire following the test, and a collection of qualitative data using semi-structured interviews with the user, including observations, will help to measure the intervention's effectiveness and understand the context. Screening phases in the treatment process will be helpful in the continuous optimisation of the experience.

Initially, testing should happen using healthy subjects to be able to estimate the effects and establish a baseline. Moroz and Carhart-Harris's (2018) suggestion to select healthy patients for phase 1 drug-only testing. The measurement instrument could then be a standardised anxiety scale questionnaire and other cognitive measures. The results can be compared from the interventional groups with the control groups.

Identifying "specific drug, dosage, and simulation combinations" (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018, p. 3), phase 2 could have patients who responded well to phase 1, see to test mixed reality in combination with psychedelics, for example, for the comedown phase.

A modification of the German VR Simulation Realism Scale (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018) could be helpful. Complementary objectives include measuring blood pressure, respiration, heart rate, and brain activity.

Riches et al. (2021) recommend incorporating participants of the first tests into further design processes, allowing personal experiences to inform design decisions. Additionally, Aday et al. (2020) mentioned the online platform Reddit as a data source for reports from users who tried psychedelics with VR for personal use that could inform design development. Future studies could incorporate nature-relatedness measures or the Disposition to Connect with Nature scale (Frecka et al., 2022).

Discussion

Psychedelic experiences can be very profound and overwhelming; recalling memories and insights can be difficult even directly after the session (Sekula et al., 2022), and integration becomes a fundamental part of the treatment and an ongoing process (Cavarra et al., 2022; Koslowski et al., 2021). Context matters profoundly (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019).

The proposition of the novel synergetic therapeutic approach of mixed reality and psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy has various potential strengths, weaknesses and limitations.

The proposition of the novel synergetic therapeutic approach of mixed reality and psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy has various potential strengths, weaknesses and limitations.

Strengths

Mixed and augmented reality blend the real world with digital layers, allowing users to have immersive experiences in their immediate environment. This allows for staying more connected to the surrounding space and reality, a point of criticism regarding digital devices to day. Technology caught up, and recent developments will make digital realities accessible to a broader range of consumers.

Urbanisation has increased globally, and people have been drifting away from nature. One-dimensional electronic devices contributed substantially to humanity's disconnection from nature, each other, and themselves. Since these technologies are means of communication and play, they are not going anywhere but augmented, and mixed reality applications might help decrease the problem of disconnection (Frecka et al., 2022).

Mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy as a tool is potentially solving several problems of current therapy models now and in the future, from congruence, scalability, economic viability, portability, and measurement of effectivity by coupling devices with biofeedback, responsive AI, and direct data transmission (Ma et al., 2021).

From a patient perspective, a mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy protocol can aid potential anxieties that come with the transition between normal and altered consciousness; it is highly personalisable, supports focus attention on the present moment, and recalls insights during integration sessions later on (Seabrook et al., 2020).

An immediate and pragmatic application of mixed reality for psychedelic-assisted therapy is even before any dosing session. For most, the idea of psychedelic states is associated with insecurities and fears. Mixed reality can simulate the visual phenomena of said state, which might help prepare patients for treatment (Aday et al., 2020), but also might help relatives and partners to get an idea and feel included.

The invention of mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy is potentially a more gentle entry before experiencing a fully immersive virtual reality-assisted psychedelic psychotherapy, something currently developed and studied, for example, by the prior mentioned startup Enosis Therapeutics (Ruiz, 2022).

Limitations and weaknesses

Not everyone is technologically averse and virtual. Mixed and augmented reality technologies might feel alien and terrifying to some, thus adding another obstacle to the already novel therapeutic treatment with psychedelic compounds.

Seabrook et al. (2020) draw attention to visual quality and the device's weight, all playing into the perspective experience. Moreover, the investment needed to build basic infrastructure for the application of these technologies in clinics is going to be considerably high, especially since treatment protocols have to be designed and tested, to begin with, as well as safety and hygiene protocols (Ma et al., 2021).

Standardisation of the treatment protocol and caution regarding potential patents of technological developments of software and hardware will make it difficult to run studies and compare data.

Finally, the potential side effects of mixed reality therapy have yet to be researched in detail for risk and harm reduction. Taking a patient out of the classic clinical setting comes with added complexity and a decrease in expectation, biasing study outcomes (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

Alternative possible practical intervention

As mentioned before, companies are currently working on virtual reality applications for psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy.

However, given the immensely positive effect nature exposure has on human health (Frecka et al., 2022; Kettner et al., 2019; Winkelman, 2021) an alternative to technological interventions could be using biophilic design, simply bringing parts of the natural world into buildings.

This could be a secure garden space within a clinic, where patients can physically hug a tree and immerse into a safe and controllable natural setting. As for extension to the patient's home, a small plant can be given to every patient as a symbol of growth and a reminder of connection.

Future research questions

Future research could explore the following:

1. How can the unique properties of augmented reality be utilised during the preparation, comedown and integration phase of a dosing session, easing the change of consciousness for the patient?
2. How can synergistic virtual or augmented reality extend the therapy impact and efficiency by allowing patients to record insights and work with said digital notes during integration?
3. How do the specific characteristics of virtual, mixed, and augmented reality affect psychedelic-assisted therapy differently, and is there a possible combined application?

Summary

Psychedelic-assisted therapy demonstrated promising results for mental and physical health (Winkelman, 2021). A full-dose therapeutic psychedelic experience comes with problems to be solved, from lack of consistency (Sekula et al., 2022), logistical and financial burdens (Cavarra et al., 2022), the extended process of integration (Koslowski et al., 2021), and impaired recollection of insights after the peak (Sekula et al., 2022).

Virtual reality, mixed reality and augmented reality technologies' capacity to affect neuroplasticity (Georgiev et al., 2021) showed enduring results for therapy (Boeldt et al., 2019; Georgiev et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021). Environments that are restorative according to the Attention Restoration Theory, a) provide the individual with a pause from the everyday environment, b) have attention anchors that maintain engagement, c) contain elements and

features that enable to hold said attention with small effort, and d) support a personal mission (Seabrook et al., 2020). All these elements can be designed into a virtual, augmented, or mixed reality experience, supporting mindfulness practice and therapeutic efficiency (Georgiev et al., 2021; Riches et al., 2021; Seabrook et al., 2020).

Studies and articles describe that nature has direct calming benefits, allowing the patient to feel a sense of interconnectedness, but that a natural setting for psychedelic-assisted therapy has its own challenges, such as privacy, potential disturbances, weather, and safety (Gandy et al., 2020). Virtual and mixed reality psychedelic-assisted therapy potentially is a synergy of a clinic's safe and controlled physical setting and natural elements, even though, in this case, digital (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

Three main benefits can be drawn from the integration of augmented reality tools into psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018):

- elevation of individual paradigms based on their complementary nature;
- possibility for highly bespoke experiences;
- possible usage of lower doses of psychedelic compounds.

Virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality technologies can solve the problem of congruity of therapy. Since it is portable, personalisable and controllable, it can offer a consistent therapeutic environment from the therapy room to the patient's home (Ma et al., 2021).

Finally, mixed reality has the potential to allow the user to have virtual interactive experiences in their immediate environments, re-connecting people back with their surroundings. In theory, a mixed reality psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy experience might help a patient transition from normal to altered consciousness and back to normal during the comedown phase. The experience design elements can build on nature's restorative and comforting properties (Frecka et al., 2022).

However, it is understood that these technologies are currently inaccessible to most and, although likely economically viable long-term, the costly development of standardised therapy, safety and hygiene protocols, and the building of infrastructure and therapist training are required first (Ma et al., 2021). Additionally, virtual reality can cause motion sickness, photosensitive seizures (Ma et al., 2021), and anxiety (Stepanova et al., 2019).

Integrating some elements of nature into the preparation and integration phases could amplify key therapeutic mechanisms and outcomes (Gandy et al., 2020); when nature is not accessible, mixed reality might offer a solution to bring the idea of nature into an urban space.

Conclusion

The present paper critically reviews the synergistic applications for virtual reality (including scarce content on mixed reality and augmented reality) and psychedelics for therapy, giving a comprehensive overview of the current state of research.

Considering that psychedelics are non-specific amplifiers (Grof, 2019) and enhance sensitivity to the internal and external environment (Carhart-Harris et al., 2018), increased attention to context and the research of the application of virtual, mixed, or augmented reality for psychedelic-assisted therapy seems justified, based on the potential long-term effectiveness after only a few treatment sessions (Moroz & Carhart-Harris, 2018).

The potential synergetic applications require further research, testing and empirical validation. Further research could explore the potential application of virtual and mixed realities as tools for recording immediate thoughts during the comedown phase, easing the transition into and out of an altered state of consciousness; for seamless and consistent psychedelic therapy experiences throughout all phases.

Mixed reality, combined with psychedelic compounds, which improve (Frecka et al., 2022; Gandy et al., 2020) relatedness, might have promising and scalable applications beyond psychotherapy.

Albert Hofmann—the first to synthesise, ingest, and learn of the psychedelic effects of LSD and the first to isolate and synthesise psilocybin—believed in the capacity of psychedelics to reconnect humanity to nature and each other (Gandy et al., 2020; Hofmann, 2008). Gandy et al. (2020) wrote that Albert Hofmann "recalled that among his most satisfying experiences were hearing people say things like 'I grew up in the city, but once I first took LSD, I returned to the forest'" (p. 10).

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